

D4.1. Recommendations on how to evolve the OTMR Toolkit under the gender lenses

Document Data	
Report Title	D4.1. Recommendations on how to evolve the OTMR Toolkit under a gender lenses
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Responsible Project Partner	FECYT
Due Date	31 December 2020
Delivery Date	
Type	Public report
Dissemination Level	Public
Keywords	Gender equality; recruitment; researchers

This project is funded by the EU. This publication has been produced with the financial support of the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 824536. The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of the authors and can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Commission.

History			
Xavier Eekhout, Izaskun Lacunza	10.12.2020	First draft	
David Lamiquiz, Leire Gartzia	16.12.2020	Peer-review	
Xavier Eekhout, Izaskun Lacunza	22.12.2020	Final version	
Xavier Eekhout	07.10.2021	Public version -Typos corrected - Further explanations to Fig 3.	

Information in this report that may influence other GEARING-ROLES tasks

Linked Task	Points of Relevance
Task 4.1	

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List of Abbreviations

EC: European Commission.

ERA: European Research Area.

GEP: Gender Equality Plan.

HRS4R: Human Resources Strategy for Researchers.

OTM-R: Open Transparent and Merit-based Recruitment.

SGHRM: Steering Group on Human Resources and Mobility. An EC advisory group composed by national experts on human resources management and mobility of researchers.

SWG HRM: Standing Working Group on Human Resources and Mobility. Currently replaces the SGHRM but is under the European Council and reports to the European Research Area and Innovation Committee (ERAC).

Executive Summary

Open, transparent and merit-based recruitment (OTM-R) ensures that the best person for the job is recruited, improving the effectiveness of national research systems, guarantees equality, especially for under-represented groups, and boosts international and transnational co-operation. The OTM-R toolkit has been developed to support research organizations in reinforcing their recruitment practices.

The Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers is key policy designed to contribute to an open labour market of researchers, which is a priority of the European Research Area. It is composed by 40 principles providing the rights and obligations of researchers and researcher employer organizations. The uptake of the principles is fostered through the implementation process known as the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R) which guides researcher performing organizations in a continuous process for improving the management of their human resources. This process applies as key step of their self-assessment the OTM-R checklist, which facilitates the organizations to evaluate their recruitment practices in order to identify gaps and plan improvements.

This reports presents the rationale and the work done within the GEARING Roles project which has led to the publication of an OTM-R checklist proposal with a strengthen gender dimension, which could potentially contribute to improving gender equality in the recruitment procedures, as well as to harmonising the HRS4R process with the preparation of institutional Gender Equality Plans.

Introduction

GEARING-Roles project

GEARING-Roles (Gender Equality Actions in Research Institutions to traNsform Gender ROLES) is a four-year (January 2019 – December 2022) Coordination and Support Action project that brings together a pan-European group of academics and industry professionals to collaborate and exchange knowledge, good practices, and lessons learned on designing, implementing, and evaluating 6 Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). The project therefore has a firm objective of challenging and transforming gender roles and identities linked to professional careers and working towards real institutional change. This multidisciplinary, multinational, and multi-sectorial collaboration will be supported by training, mentoring activities, awareness raising campaigns as well as bi-annual videos and podcasts and annual networking events.

The European Research Area

The European Research Area (ERA) was launched in 2000 with the ambition to create a single, borderless market for research, innovation and technology across the EU. Thus, its aim is to achieve the free circulation of researchers and knowledge enabling:

- More effective national research systems
- Trans-national co-operation and competition
- Gender equality
- Optimal circulation, access to and transfer of scientific knowledge
- Open labour market for researchers

In order to achieve an open labour market for researchers, an important policy document was published by the European Commission (EC) in 2005, the [Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers](#) (Charter & Code from hereinafter). This document is composed of 40 principles detailing the rights and obligations of researchers, as well as the rights and obligations of organizations recruiting researchers.

Since its publication, the Charter & Code has become a widely accepted framework for human resource departments in research organisations, with [more than 1200 organisations](#) across Europe having endorsed it publicly.

The Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R)

In an effort to roll out the Charter and Code, throughout Europe, the EC launched the '[HR Excellence in Research Award](#)' which recognises institutions making progress in aligning their human resources policies to the 40 principles of the Charter & Code, based on a customized action plan/HR strategy. This aligning process is called *Human Resources Strategy for Researchers* (HRS4R), and to date, [almost 600 organisations](#) across Europe have implemented it and received the award.

One of the key aims of the Charter and Code and the HRS4R is to contribute to the development of a common open, transparent, merit based recruitment (OTM-R) for researchers in Europe. OTM-R ensures that the best person for the job is recruited, guarantees equal opportunities and access for all, facilitates developing an international portfolio (cooperation, competition, mobility) and makes research careers more attractive.

Nevertheless, as of 2013, the [ERA Progress Report](#) noted that "A co-ordinated effort is needed by Member States and institutions to ensure that all research positions are subject to open, transparent and merit-based recruitment practices". Due to this, the ERA Steering Group of Human Resources and Mobility (SGHRM) established a working group with representatives from 15 Member States and Associated Countries, together with the European Commission and key stakeholder organizations to develop a toolkit in the sense of a step-by-step guide to improve the research performing organizations' recruitment procedures and practices. The full description of the group's composition, work and results can be found in the report [Open, Transparent and Merit-based Recruitment of Researchers](#), although the most relevant output was the OTM-R checklist aimed at facilitating the self-assessment of institutions towards achieving this.

This checklist includes a detailed list of criteria any institution should cover when evaluating their recruitment policies and, in particular, their advertising, selection and evaluation, and appointment phases:

OTM-R checklist for organisations					
	Open	Trans- parent	Merit- based	Answer: ++ Yes, <i>completely</i> +/- Yes, <i>substantially</i> -/+ Yes, <i>partially</i> -- No	*Suggested indicators (or form of measurement)
OTM-R system					
1. Have we published a version of our OTM-R policy online (in the national language and in English)?	x	x	x		[web link]
2. Do we have an internal guide setting out clear OTM-R procedures and practices for all types of positions?	x	x	x		[Date of latest update; ensure that it is sent to all staff]
3. Is everyone involved in the process sufficiently trained in the area of OTM-R?	x	x	x		- Existence of training programs for OTM-R - Number of staff following training in OTM-R
4. Do we make (sufficient) use of e-recruitment tools?	x	x			Web-based tool for (all) the stages in the recruitment process
5. Do we have a quality control system for OTM-R in place?	x	x	x		
6. Does our current OTM-R policy encourage external candidates to apply?	x	x	x		Trend in the share of applicants from outside the organisation
7. Is our current OTM-R policy in line with policies to attract researchers from abroad?	x	x	x		Trend in the share of applicants from abroad
8. Is our current OTM-R policy in line with policies to attract underrepresented groups?	x	x	x		Trend in the share of applicants among underrepresented groups (frequently women)
9. Is our current OTM-R policy in line with policies to provide attractive working conditions for researchers?	x	x	x		Trend in the share of applicants from outside the organisation
10. Do we have means to monitor whether the most suitable researchers apply?					
Advertising and application phase					
11. Do we have clear guidelines or templates (e.g., EURAXESS) for advertising positions?	x	x			

12. Do we include in the job advertisement references/links to all the elements foreseen in the relevant section of the toolkit?	x	x			
13. Do we make full use of EURAXESS to ensure our research vacancies reach a wider audience?	x	x			- The share of job adverts posted on EURAXESS; - Trend in the share of applicants recruited from outside the organisation/abroad
14. Do we make use of other job advertising tools?	x	x			
15. Do we keep the administrative burden to a minimum for the candidate?	x				
Selection and evaluation phase					
16. Do we have clear rules governing the appointment of selection committees?		x	x		Statistics on the composition of panels
17. Do we have clear rules concerning the composition of selection committees?		x	x		Written guidelines
18. Are the committees sufficiently gender-balanced?		x	x		
19. Do we have clear guidelines for selection committees which help to judge 'merit' in a way that leads to the best candidate being selected?			x		Written guidelines
Appointment phase					
20. Do we inform all applicants at the end of the selection process?		x			
21. Do we provide adequate feedback to interviewees?		x			
22. Do we have an appropriate complaints mechanism in place?		x			Statistics on complaints
Overall assessment					
23. Do we have a system in place to assess whether OTM-R delivers on its objectives?					

This checklist was eventually included into the HRS4R process as part of the initial phase with the gap assessment and initial action plan that organisations need to present to be acknowledged with the HR Excellence in Research Award (see figure 1).

Figure 1. HRS4R procedure chart, including the OTM-r Checklist

As described above, the HRS4R was designed as a tool to foster institutional change that can become real in the practice through a process in which the organizations can benchmark the management of their human resources to the principles of the Charter & Code, in order to design an action plan aimed at improving their activities. Any process of organizational change is generally complex and involves changes at several levels of analysis (Weick & Quinn, 1999), so this process is also progressive and includes future assessments of the action plan's implementation that will serve to ensure its effectiveness. The process also foresees the involvement of the different stakeholders in the organization including the institutional direction, human resources staff, managerial staff and, of course, the researchers themselves.

This way, the HRS4R has a number of parallelisms with the preparation of institutional GEPs. On one hand, GEPs are a key factor to address the ERA's objective of improving gender equality and are instruments to encourage institutional change in research organizations.

On the other, the process and institutional agents involved are similar, as generally speaking, the process of a GEP can be summarized in in the following actions:

- Conducting impact assessment and audits of procedures and practices, to identify gender bias.
- Implementing innovative strategies to correct bias.
- Setting targets and monitoring progress via indicators.

It is important to highlight though that a GEP by definition cannot be part of broader strategy or plan (e.g., a strategy to manage your human resources), which includes a gender dimension. Nevertheless there are possibilities to improve the connection between them to align and reinforce each other, at the same time the work of the people involved in their preparation and implementation is optimized.

Task 4.1 Promotion and evolution of the OTM-r toolkit towards a gender-equality friendly OTM-R

Although it is expected that more transparent processes should have a direct impact in more gender balanced recruitment procedure, we understand that the OTM-R checklist in particular can be further strengthened to foster recruitment practices that favour gender equality more actively.

As a matter of fact, the current version of the checklist already addresses gender through some of its items for instance, through the existence of gender equality in the selection committees (see original OTM-R checklist above). Nevertheless, as highlighted in the recent [She Figures Report](#), gender biases in recruitment procedures in general (not only in research), still persist. Indeed the report, confirmed that more than one third of Europeans believe that men are more ambitious than women (35%), or that almost seven in ten respondents think women are more likely than men to make decisions based on their emotions (69 %).

The persistence of these gender biases prompted GEARING-Roles to revisit the OTM-R checklist to assess which parts of the document could be strengthened from a gender perspective to further avoid gender biases in the recruitment of researchers.

In order to collect feedback from GEARING Roles GEP implementing institutions, as well as other relevant sources (e.g., sister projects) to issue recommendations of how the OTM-R could be evolved, three channels were used:

1. Training workshop: Building a gender equality plan – the role of participative methods (June 20-21 2019)

2. Webinar Good Practices for Achieving Gender Equality in Recruitment and Career Development Of Researchers In Europe (June 26 2019)
3. GEARING Roles OTM-R Training Workshop (November 28 2019)

Training workshop: *Building a gender equality plan – the role of participative methods* (Oxford, June 20-21 2019)

This was one of the several trainings provided by Yellow Window to support GEP implementers of the GEARING Roles project. More specifically, the training addressed participative methods which will help the institutions along the process of designing and implementing their GEPs.

This training was organized together with the first GEARING Roles pairing hosted by Oxford Brookes University, and counted with the participation of all GEP implementing institutions (University of Deusto, Oxford Brookes University, Institute of Geography and Spatial Planning of the University of Lisbon, Sabanci University, Faculty of Arts University of Ljubljana and Estonian Research Council). The training addressed through practical exercises participative methods needed by the GEP implementers in order to address the different steps needed to develop and implement their GEPs.

One of these exercises was the Lotus Blossom which allows participants to brainstorm around a certain problem providing ideas in tow waves (first level ideas are copied into the second level, to generate new ideas, and so on). The exercise, which was primarily aimed at getting familiarized with the methodology, addressed the problem *How to avoid gender bias during a face-to-face interview?*, turned out to be extremely useful for compiling recommendations from GEP implementing partners on how to updated the OTM-R Checklist as it facilitated a structured discussion leading to potential recruitment practices that could be implemented to avoid gender biases, and thus feed into a gendered-strengthened checklist (Fig. 3).

LOTUS BLOSSOM: how to avoid gender bias during a face-to-face interview ?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under grant agreement no. 8218736

Figure 3. Result of Lotus Blossom methodology to address the *problem How to avoid gender bias during a face-to-face interview?* This technique allows addressing a central issue breaking it down to components which are then also addressed by more detailed items.

Webinar *Good Practices for Achieving Gender Equality in Recruitment and Career Development Of Researchers In Europe* (June 26 2019)

This webinar took place on June 27th 2019 focusing on sharing good practices in supporting researcher careers for achieving gender equality. The webinar included presentations from the University of Zurich, University of Vigo and the Norwegian University of Science and Technology, which provided shared their institutional practices related with job advertisement, recruitment, promotion and career development (Fig. 2).

Agenda: *Good practices for achieving gender equality in recruitment and career development of researchers*

10:00-10:20	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome and aim of the workshop
10:20-10:35	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Charter and Code <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➢ Izaskun Lacunza, Fundación Española para la Ciencia y la Tecnología.
10:35-10:50	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive actions in the performance assessment of female researchers at the Universidad de Vigo <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➢ Águeda Gómez, Equality Unit at Universidad de Vigo, Spain.
10:50-11:05	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender equality in academic career development in the University of Zurich <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➢ Alexandra Zingg , ETH Zurich, Switzerland.
11:05-11:30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools for a better gender balance in academia <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➢ Svandis Benediktsdottir, Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) • Joint discussion. How could the Charter and Code be improved to better foster gender equality in research?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, under grant agreement no. 824536

Figure 2. Agenda of the webinar *Good Practices For Achieving Gender Equality In Recruitment And Career Development Of Researchers In Europe*.

As an overarching theme across all presentations were the connections between the ERA priorities Open Labour Market for Researchers and GENDER EQUALITY particularly focused around the Charter & Code and its implementation through the HRS4R.

The webinar can be found in the GEARING Roles website and had 39 participants including representatives from GEARING-Roles consortium, partners from other sister projects and EURAXESS staff.

The good practices presented and the audience composition provided a perfect arena to consult on possible actions to foster gender equality in the advertising and application phase, the selection and evaluation phase, the appointment and/or through career development support.

The webinar can be found in the [GEARING Roles website](#).

GEARING Roles OTM-R Training Workshop (Lisbon, November 28 2019)

The 1st Consortium Meeting of GEARING-Roles organised in Lisbon after the 1st GEARING-Roles Conference provided the possibility to organize a training for the GEARING Roles partners addressing in detail the connections between the Charter & Code and the OTM-r checklist to guide a structured discussion of how the checklist's gender dimension could be further reinforced.

The first part of the content was addressed through a quiz (Kahoot) covering the following question (correct answers in bold):

The European Research Area (ERA) Priorities include...

- gender equality and gender mainstreaming in research
- an open labour market for researchers
- more effective national research systems
- **all of the previous options**

CHOOSE THE WRONG OPTION: Some of the measures the EC has put in place to foster open labour market for researchers are

- Launching the EURAXESS - Researchers in Motion initiative
- Creating the EURAXESS Jobs online platform
- Issuing the European Charter and Code for researchers
- **Requesting MS to invest above 3% of their GDP in R+D+I**

CHOOSE THE WRONG OPTION: The main objectives of the Charter and Code are...

- Achieving a common European "language" in HHRR in research
- Describing rights and obligations of researchers
- **A minimum requirement mandatory to apply for EU funding**
- Describing rights and obligations of research organizations

CHOOSE THE WRONG OPTION: The Charter and Code are 40 principles around the following concepts

- Ethical and professional aspects
- Recruitment and selection

- **Access rights to audiovisual content**
- Working condition, training and development

There are specific principles in the C&C addressing gender equality

- **True**
- False

The HR Excellence in Research award recognizes institutions with a plan to align their policies to the C&C

- **True**
- False

The HR Excellence in Research award is obtained by

- (1) Letter of endorsement to C&C
- (1) Proposal to the EC (2) External expert evaluation
- **(1) Gap analysis of HR Policies (2) Action plan (3) peer review**
- (1) Paying a fee to the European HR Logo Audit Service

This continuous implementation process is known as...

- LV-426
- **HRS4R**
- R2D2
- HR-4S

CHOOSE THE WRONG OPTION: What is the relation between EURAXESS and the HR Award?

- EURAXESS promotes the C&C and its implementation through the HRS4R
- The HRS4R is managed through the EURAXESS Portal
- **Only institutions with the HR Award can become EURAXESS members**
- Offers from institutions with the HR Award are highlighted in EURAXESS Jobs

CHOOSE THE WRONG OPTION: Forty two (42)...

- is the answer to the meaning of life, the universe, and everything
- are the number of EURAXESS National Networks
- **are the principles of the C&C**
- is the result of 7x6

How many European Institutions have received the HR Excellence in Research Award?

- 125
- 1145
- 90
- **502**

The OTM-R toolkit builds on the C&C principles related to the Recruitment of Researchers.

- **True**
- False

The OTM-R Toolkit integrates all the existing knowledge about gender equality good practices in recruitment

- True
- **False**

Following the quiz and explanation of the correct replies, the structured discussion was done over the original OTM-R checklist (see above) collecting recommendations of how to update it in order to strengthen its gender dimension.

OTM-R seen through gender equality lenses

Together, these three project activities allowed the compiling of ideas on ways in which the recruitment practices of any given institution could be strengthened to foster greater gender equality, such as. The list below collates the different ideas proposed by the participants of these three activities, grouped under the main headings of the OTMR-R Checklist.

Recruitment system as whole:

- Keeping sex-disaggregated data on all parts of the recruitment process (applications, shortlisting and appointed).
- Implement mechanisms to support disadvantaged candidates.
- Clear guidelines and transparency about the overall recruitment process for all potential candidates.
- Legal commitment on behalf of the institution to non-biased recruitment and systems to ensure application (e.g., audits, written commitment of panel members, etc.).

Advertising and application phase:

- Clear criteria which will be assessed during the selection and evaluation phase.
- Ensure gender sensitive language is used, taking into account gendered concepts such as “excellence.”
- Highlight the existence of institutional policies against sexism, sexual harassment and gender-based violence.
- Include references to any equity measures already in place (e.g., dual career services, work-life balance policies, child-care facilities, mentoring, etc.).
- Include relevant information on career progression.

Selection and evaluation phase:

- Diversity in the composition of selection committees, which includes not only respecting gender balance but also intersectionality.
- Systematic trainings on gender equality and unconscious biases for selection committee members, and institutional recognition of participating in such trainings.
- Meeting and greeting protocols for the selection committee members.
- Consistent questions for all candidates, addressing only relevant criteria.
- Applying pre-defined role plays to committee members.
- External selection committee members (e.g., from other disciplines, institutions and/or countries) and observers (e.g., a representative from gender unit).
- The implementation of measures to facilitate blind evaluations (e.g., blind CVs, blind interviews using technological resources, etc.).
- Support measures to allow candidates to participate in the selection and evaluation procedure (family friendly scheduling of interviews, flexibility, support for care obligations, etc.).

The appointment phase:

- Appointing all underrepresented groups candidates that meet the required threshold.
- Providing constructive feedback to all candidates, regardless of being selected or not.
- Establishing anonymous feedback mechanisms about the application process for all candidates.

These specific ideas were then used by FECYT to translate them into potential updates to the OTM- Checklist. The way in which this was done was either by proposing new principles or subprinciples, by including reflexions about how the different principles

(existing or new) are expected to contribute to gender equality, and by suggesting gender-strengthened indicators. All details can be found in the next section.

OTM-R Checklist seen through gender equality lenses

It is important to highlight that the OTM-R checklist aims to help institutions assess their recruitment policies, at the same time it provides recommendations on how to improve them in order to become more open, transparent and merit-based. Keeping this in mind, a first attempt at a review of the OTM-R checklist is presented below which includes many of the ideas mentioned above.

The table below is based on a collective discussion within the GEARING-Roles project on how the OTM-R Checklist could be updated to foster gender equality in the researcher recruitment processes.

THE OPEN, TRANSPARENT, MERIT BASED RECRUITMENT TOOLKIT

SEEN THROUGH GENDER EQUALITY LENSES. A FIRST ATTEMPT

All the suggestions are highlighted in purple

OPEN TRANSPARENT MERTIT BASED RECRUITMENT SYSTEM (OTMR) AS A WHOLE

Principles /Subprinciples	Some ideas on how these principles and subprinciples could support gender equality	Suggested indicators (or form of measurement)
1. Have we published a version of our OTM-R policy online (in the national language and in English)?		[web link]
2. Do we have an internal guide setting out clear OTM-R procedures and practices for all types of positions?		[Date of latest update; ensure that it is sent to all staff]
3. Is everyone involved in the process sufficiently trained in the area of OTM-R?		- Existence of training programs for OTM-R - Number of staff following training in OTM-R

<p>3a. Does this training involve awareness about the underrepresentation of women in research careers?</p>	<p>It essential that all the staff involved in the recruitment of researchers is aware of the “leaky pipeline” effect which affects research careers and the reasons behind it.</p>	<p>Training content</p>
<p>4. Do we make (sufficient) use of e-recruitment tools?</p>		<p>Web-based tool for (all) the stages in the recruitment process</p>
<p>4a. Do these tools support the application of disadvantaged candidates?</p>		<p>Tools allowing disadvantaged candidates to apply</p>
<p>5. Do we have a quality control system for OTM-R in place?</p>		
<p>5a. Does this system allow to keep sex disaggregated data on all parts of the recruitment process?</p>	<p>Sex disaggregated data is essential to monitor progress on gender equality and plan correction measures.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Phases of the recruitment process in which sex disaggregated data are kept - Reports with indicators
<p>5b. Is the system subject to any legal commitment to non-biased recruitment?</p>	<p>Institutional policies supporting gender equality and diversity should influence recruitment practices.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Institutional gender and/or diversity equality plans
<p>6. Does our current OTM-R policy encourage external candidates to apply?</p>		<p>Trend in the share of applicants from outside the organization</p>
<p>7. Is our current OTM-R policy in line with policies to attract researchers from abroad?</p>		<p>Trend in the share of applicants from abroad</p>

<p>8. Is our current OTM-R policy in line with policies to attract underrepresented groups?</p>	<p>There is already a lot of knowledge on how to set up policies to foster gender equality in the recruitment of researchers. Our institutional OTM-r policy should explicitly refer to these.</p>	<p>Trend in the share of applicants among underrepresented groups (frequently women)</p>
<p>9. Is our current OTM-R policy in line with policies to provide attractive working conditions for researchers?</p>		<p>Trend in the share of applicants from outside the organization</p>
<p>10. Do we have means to monitor whether the most suitable researchers apply?</p>		
<p>ADVERTISING AND APPLICATION PHASE</p>		
<p>Principles /Subprinciples</p>	<p>Some ideas on how these principles and subprinciples could support gender equality</p>	<p>Suggested indicators (or form of measurement)</p>
<p>11. Do we have clear guidelines or templates (e.g., EURAXESS) for advertising positions?</p>	<p>Include criteria that will be assessed during the selection and evaluation phase</p>	

These good practices may include:

- I. Ensure gender sensitive language is applied (e.g., avoid gendered concepts such as “excellence”).
- II. Highlight any existing institutional policies against sexism, sexual harassment and gender-based violence in your institution.
- III. Highlight in the ad any existing institutional equity policy (work-life balance policies, child-care facilities, etc.).
- IV. Include any relevant information regarding career progression in the institution.

Trend of women in the share of applicants

11a. Do these guidelines follow good practices on the advertising phase in order to attract women?

12. Do we include in the job advertisement references/links to all the elements foreseen in the relevant section of the toolkit?

13. Do we make full use of EURAXESS to ensure our research vacancies reach a wider audience?

- The share of job adverts posted on EURAXESS;
- Trend in the share of applicants recruited from outside the organisation/abroad

14. Do we make use of other job advertising tools?

15. Do we keep the administrative burden to a minimum for the candidate?

SELECTION AND EVALUATION PHASE

Principles /Subprinciples	Some ideas on how these principles and subprinciples could support gender equality	Suggested indicators (or form of measurement)
<p>X. Are there measures in place to make sure that the interviews are compatible with good work-life balance practices?</p>	<p>Caring obligations tend to fall over women, so it is important to facilitate the possibility to participate in the recruitment process by allowing sufficient time between notification and interview, use family-friendly schedules, using online tools, etc.</p>	
<p>16. Do we have clear rules governing the appointment of selection committees?</p>	<p>In order to minimise unconscious biases, measures to ensure diverse committees can be implemented. Beyond gender balance (principle 18), committees could include external members (other disciplines, other institutions, other countries)</p>	<p>Statistics on the composition of panels</p>
<p>X. Are selection committees duly trained on how to perform open, transparent, bias-free, merit-based recruitment processes?</p>	<p>Apart from trainings on gender equality in research careers, committee members should be trained on unconscious biases to ensure these aren't enacted during the selection and evaluation phase.</p>	<p>Training about unconscious biases</p>
<p>17. Do we have clear rules concerning the composition of selection committees?</p>	<p>The attendance of a HR officer will make sure that the process is following the OTM-r policy and that the selection committee member's opinions are given the same weight (democratic committees)</p>	<p>Written guidelines</p>
<p>18. Are the committees sufficiently gender-balanced?</p>	<p>A gender balance committee will contribute to gender equality during the selection and evaluation phase.</p>	

<p>18a. Is intersectionality taken into consideration when setting the selection committees?</p>	<p>Intersectional discrimination should also be addressed in the selection committees for example, though their composition and/or by providing trainings.</p>	<p>Trainings on intersectional discrimination</p>
<p>19. Do we have clear guidelines for selection committees which help to judge 'merit' in a way that leads to the best candidate being selected?</p>	<p>Current practices about how merit is being assessed in academia are being questioned by many different communities (open science's, gender equality, etc.). More and more institutions are evolving their definition of "merit" to foster a more open, gender-equal academic community.</p>	<p>Written guidelines</p>
<p>APPOINTMENT PHASE</p>		
<p>Principles /Subprinciples</p>	<p>Some ideas on how these principles and subprinciples could support gender equality</p>	<p>Suggested indicators (or form of measurement)</p>
<p>20. Do we inform all applicants at the end of the selection process?</p>	<p>Providing constructive, homogenous feedback to all candidates can help avoiding any unconscious biases that may have influenced the selection phase.</p>	
<p>21. Do we provide adequate feedback to interviewees?</p>	<p>Establishing feedback mechanisms about the recruitment process for all candidates can help identify any practices hampering gender equality.</p>	
<p>22. Do we have an appropriate complaints mechanism in place?</p>		<p>Statistics on complaints</p>

OVERALL ASSESSMENT

Principle	Some ideas on how these principles and subprinciples could support gender equality	Suggested indicators (or form of measurement)
<p>23. Do we have a system in place to assess whether OTM-R delivers on its objectives?</p> <p>23a. Do these objectives include clear gender equality indicators?</p>		

This table can be downloaded from the [GEARING-Roles website](#).

Disseminations of results and further discussions

The proposal to update the OTM-R Checklist under a gender lens was made public on March 2020 through the [GEARING Roles website](#).

A workshop proposal was presented to the XI European Conference on Gender Equality in Higher Education originally planned to take place in Madrid on the 16-18 September 2020 with the participation of GEARING-Roles, sister projects, the EC and the host institution which has obtained the HR Excellence in Research Award. The content of the workshop was proposed at the more general level of the Charter and Code but the GEARING Roles OTM-R proposal was going to be included as part of the discussion (Fig 4.). Unfortunately, the conference was postponed due to the COVID-19 pandemic and is not expected to take place until September 2021. The workshop proposal has been kept submitted for the conference on 2021.

ABSTRACT FOR THE XI EUROPEAN CONFERENCE ON GENDER EQUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

In 2005, the European Commission adopted a European Charter for Researchers and a Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers. These two documents, addressed to researchers as well as research employers and funders in both the public and private sectors, are key elements in the EU's policy to boost researchers' careers.

The implementation of the Charter & Code principles by European research institutions contributes to the construction of the European Research Area by defining a common ground of rights and obligations of researchers and their institutions. In order to foster the uptake of the Charter and Code, H2020 beneficiaries are explicitly asked to do their best efforts to align their policies towards these principles.

As of yet, 507 European organizations have received the HR Excellence in Research award as an acknowledgement of the European Commission of their action plans in order to align their human resources policies with the Charter & Code.

Among the Charter & Code, gender equality is explicitly addressed in some principles (non-discrimination, recruitment of researchers and gender balance of staff). However, there is still room for improvement so that gender and intersectionality becomes a crosscutting dimension of the Charter & Code. By doing so, both the Charter and Code and gender equality plans of European institutions could be mutually benefited and aligned to address more efficiently the "leaky pipeline" phenomenon in research organizations at the level of human resources management.

During this workshop, an interactive session with the audience is planned in order to gather opinions from gender equality in research experts on how to develop a version of the Charter and Code with a crosscutting gender perspective. These results will be further discussed in iterative sessions with the GEARING-Roles project and a final proposal issued for public deliberation with different stakeholders.

This project is funded by the EU. This publication has been produced with the financial support of the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 824536 The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of the authors and can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Commission.

Figure 4. Screenshot of the GEARING Roles workshop proposal submitted to the XI European Conference on Gender Equality in Higher Education

This project result has also been shared with the H2020 project [CASPER](#) which examines the feasibility of establishing a European award/certification system for gender equality for Research Performing Organizations. The work done has been included as part of their report [State of the Art Analysis: mapping the awarding certification landscape in HE/Research in Europe](#), which reviews EU policy frameworks targeting quality and excellence in research and education, linked to the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R).

In the same line, being aware about the fact that the ERAC Standing Working Group (SWG) on Human Resources and Mobility (chaired by a FECYT representative) and the ERAC SWG on Gender in Research and Innovation (GRI) and on Open Science and Innovation (OSI) are currently working on a joint revision of the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers (Charter and Code) from a gender and open science perspective, this result has also been shared with the assigned task force along the Spring of 2020.

At the time of this report, the work of the task force is still ongoing and includes a stakeholder consultation on their work along the first trimester of 2021. As the GEARING-Roles OTM-R reflects a possible way on how the implementation of a gender-strengthen Charter and Code could look, there are plans to present the result in this forum too.